

SONOGRAPHIC EVALUATION OF POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME (PCOS) IN MARRIED AND UNMARRIED FEMALES OF LAHORE BEFORE MENOPAUSE

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Abstract

Background: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a common endocrine disorder with diverse clinical manifestations affecting 5–10% of reproductive-aged women. The main characteristic is a rise in androgen production by the gonads. Utilizing ovarian biology, this review to explain a method to promote comprehension and explanation of PCOS. While extensive research has been conducted on the clinical, hormonal, and metabolic aspects of PCOS, limited attention has been given to exploring the potential influence of marital status on the sonographic findings of PCOS. Females diagnosed with PCOS, aged between 18 and 45 years, who have not reached menopause, are included in this study. The sample size was 73. Sonographic evaluation was included the assessment of ovarian morphology, follicle count, ovarian volume, stromal echogenicity, and the presence of follicular cysts. Understanding the impact of marital status on PCOS can aid in personalized diagnosis, management, and counseling for affected individuals. Further research in this area is crucial to unravel the complex nature of PCOS and its varied clinical presentations.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES: This study aims to evaluate and compare the sonographic features of PCOS in married and unmarried females of Pakistan before menopause. Analyze proper criteria of diagnosis of polycystic ovaries and to distinguish the role of ultrasound.

MATERIALS AND METHOD: This study was conducted by using convenient sampling technique. Data from 73 patients of different hospitals were investigated by use of Ultrasound. Each report was viewed and diagnosis was made. The collected data was then evaluated by using IBM's SPSS STATISTICS.

RESULTS: Out of 73 patients who were affected by PCOS 54 (74%) were unmarried and 19 (26%) were married. So, the ratio of PCOS was higher in unmarried then married females. The age of PCOS patients included in this research was between 15 to 45 (before menopause). 45(61%) women with middle

socioeconomic status, 37(50%) were students, 41(56%) had taken previous PCOS treatment, 41(56%) had reproductive issues, 48(65%) had irregular menses, 59(80%) had hirsutism, 48(65%) had acne, 44(60%) had weight issues, 50(68%) had physical activity, 50(68%) had low stress level, 32(43%) had anxiety occasionally, 55(75%) had no genetics of PCOS.

CONCLUSION: The relationship between PCOS and their effects on quality of life is a topic of vast debate, and we still do not know how PCOS cause a large number of complications. We observed direct correlation between PCOS and irregular or delayed menses and having no children that can be taken as a symptom of PCOS diagnosis. According to the findings of study prevalence of signs and symptoms of PCOS are increasing but females are not aware of PCOS although its signs and symptoms were present in many of them. Furthermore, study indicates PCOS is more than in unmarried females than married females. Majority of females do not consult gynecologist unless there is severe or life threatening problem or disease. Therefore, females should consult gynecologist at least once in a year for their better health issues.

INTRODUCTION

Stein and Leventhal are considered to have been the first investigators of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS); however, in 1721 Vallisneri, an Italian scientist, described a married, infertile woman with shiny, white-surfaced, and pigeon-egg-sized ovaries. It was not until the early 1990s at a National Institutes of Health (NIH) sponsored conference on PCOS those formal diagnostic criteria were proposed and subsequently widely used. (1)

The endocrine disease polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is complex and most common in reproductive aged women with prevalence between 5% to 15%. PCOS can be diagnosed based on Rotterdam criteria that is: (1) anovulation (2) hyperandrogenism (3) polycystic ovaries. The metabolic abnormalities (insulin resistance and overweight/obesity), which are frequently observed in PCOS patients and may be important in the development of the condition, are nevertheless included in the diagnostic criteria. (1)

It frequently begins in adolescence and is characterized by ovarian malfunction and hormonal imbalance. The International Evidence-Based PCOS Guidelines, which place an emphasis on PCOS prevention, screening, and treatment across the reproductive age, were created in response to the recognition of these problems in the care of adolescents and women with PCOS. (2)

PCOS is the result of the interaction of genetic predispositions, epigenetic modifications, and

environmental exposure with intrinsic ovarian abnormalities in steroidogenesis, neuroendocrine dysfunction, insulin resistance/hyperinsulinemia, nutritional excess, ectopic fat accumulation, inflammatory markers and insulin resistance/hyperinsulinemia. No single gene flaw has been identified, despite apparent autosomal dominant family patterns. (2)

PCOS is a complicated and multifaceted etiology that includes genetic, environmental, and transgenerational elements. These sources fuel the mechanisms of an imbalanced hypothalamus-pituitary-ovarian axis signaling that encourages the hyperandrogenism of the ovaries and the adrenal glands. The condition is also plagued by insulin resistance, which is made worse by adipose tissue buildup and malfunction brought on by hyperandrogenism, lip toxicity, and oxidative stress. Therefore, the complete clinical spectrum of the disease includes defects in metabolism, reproduction, and psychology.

The existence of 12 or more follicles with a diameter of 2 to 9 mm or an ovarian volume greater than 10 mL in the follicular phase are the main diagnostic criteria for PCOS. An increase in stromal tissue is another characteristic. More than 80% of women with a clinical diagnosis of PCOS may experience these morphological alterations in the ovary. (6)

Patients with PCOS are more likely than healthy women to experience psychological issues and a lower

quality of life (QoL), in addition to the well-known cardiovascular and metabolic abnormalities.(21)

When compared to multifollicular and control groups, patients with PCOS had significantly larger ovarian volume, area, stroma, and mean S/A ratios. For ovarian volume (13.21 mL), area (7.00 cm²), stroma (1.95 cm²), and S/A ratio (0.34), cut-off values have been established. The sensitivity for diagnosing PCOS varied between 21%, 4%, 62%, and 100%. The testosterone levels had the strongest connection with the S/A ratio.(30)

In order to reduce the risk of developing chronic diseases, exercise and physical activity are advised as the first line of treatment in the Endocrine Society Clinical Practice Guidelines on the Diagnosis and Treatment of PCOS. However, specific recommendations on the type of exercise are not made. The PCOS Australian Alliance adult guidelines recommended at least 150 minutes per week of moderate-intensity physical activity, of which 90 minutes should be moderate-to-high intensity aerobic activity, to maintain health and/or help prevent chronic comorbidities by reducing body weight, based on a 2011 systematic review of aerobic exercise (e.g., walking, cycling) for women with PCOS.(32)

Objective:

The aim of the study is to evaluate the sonographic evaluation of PCOS in married and unmarried females of Pakistan before menopause.

Rationale:

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a common endocrine disorder with diverse clinical manifestations affecting 5–10% of reproductive-aged women. The main characteristic is a rise in androgen production by the gonads. Utilizing ovarian biology, this review to explain a method to promote comprehension and explanation of PCOS. While extensive research has been conducted on the clinical, hormonal, and metabolic aspects of PCOS, limited attention has been given to exploring the potential influence of marital status on the sonographic findings of PCOS. I want to give a different perspective to the physicians through my research that Ultrasound is highly sensitive in terms of PCOS. With the help of Ultrasound better results can be acquired

and rapid diagnosis can be made. It is also beneficial in further prognosis of the disease.

Significance:

This study will help the researchers to evaluate sonographic evaluation of PCOS in married and unmarried females of Pakistan before menopause.

It will also encourage physicians to investigate PCOS through Ultrasound for early diagnosis of the disease.

This study will also provide a significant insight that Ultrasound, in addition to rapid diagnosis is also beneficial in further prognosis and treatment of the disease.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Jacob P Christ., 2018) conducted a cross sectional observational study on PCOS. The patients were included from hospital and research centers. The sample size was 50. He stated that S/A was inversely correlated with these factors, androgen indicators and LH: FSH were positively correlated with stromal index. Larger follicles (5-8 mm) exhibited beneficial relationships, but follicles under 4 mm were negatively related with a number of metabolic indicators. Cardio metabolic parameters were not linked to stromal markers.(34)

(Elysia and Twickler. 2016) conducted cross sectional observational study on PCOS. 151 women with sonographically diagnosed polycystic ovaries had their medical records and ultrasounds examined. One hundred twenty-eight individuals had polycystic ovaries according to official sonographic criteria, and 115 of them (89.8%) had polycystic ovarian syndrome ($p = .009$). The polycystic ovarian syndrome might be significantly predicted by lower gravidity, unusual bleeding (35)

(Fozia Tabassum., 2022) conducted case control study on PCOS. The sample size was 300. Compared to 78% of the control group, 97% of PCOS cases were overall under the age of 30. 60 percent of PCOS cases were students, and nearly 54 percent had advanced degrees. 39% of people were students, and only 15% had a higher degree ($P 0.001$). A higher proportion of PCOS patients (16%) are associated with higher BMIs (>30).

(Nadia Ashraf, Aasma Hanif, .2022) made studies on PCOS. The study design was descriptive case series. The sample size was 100. Patients with menstrual

abnormalities made up 72% of the Cases.56 percentage of patients had a BMI over 25 kg/m2.Patients with hirsutism made up 72% of the population. 38% of patients were single, while 62% of patients overall were married. 24 (38.7%) of the patients who were married had main infertility, while 17 (27.4%) had secondary infertility.44% of the individuals exhibited elevated total serum testosterone levels.(36)

(Tahir Gaffar., 2023) conducted cross sectional observational study on PCOS. 109 individuals were evaluated, with a mean age of 26.02 + 8.66 years. 44 (40.37%) were considered obese, and 13 (11.93%) were overweight. The average BMI was 26.98 kg/m2 + 7.24. 75 people (68.8% of the population) reported menstrual abnormalities. The three clinical signs of PCOS that were most common were obesity, hirsutism, and irregular periods. Hormonal alterations were rather typical. (37)

(Muhammad Junaid., 2022) Using a self-administered questionnaire, a descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among women in Clang Valley, Malaysia. This survey attracted 410 respondents in total. The results showed that 43 (10.49%) respondents had PCOS medically diagnosed, 11 (2.68%) had PCOS identified based on signs and symptoms, and 135 (32.93%) had PCOS suspected. Nearly half of the respondents reported poor knowledge of PCOS (47.30%) and poor PCOS practice (47.60%).Nearly half of the respondents had inadequate awareness of and behaviors relevant to PCOS's health.(38)

(Zarmina Khan, .2017) Used mixed methodology approach in Quetta's public universities, focusing on questionnaire-based assessment and educational opportunities. The sample size was 451 women. The study's findings showed that 374 (72.5%) of the respondents were unaware of PCOS and learn more by reading the brochure. 407 (90.2%) of the subjects had sufficient understanding about PCOS following educational intervention. The study found that 79 (17.5%) people had PCOS suspicion, 16 (3.5%) had the condition officially diagnosed based on signs and symptoms, and 25 (5.5%) already had the condition.(39)

(Sumaira Ishaq., 2018) conducted study on PCOS.She used convenience-sampling technique. The Sample size was 150. The findings were given as mean S.E.M. The Student's t-test (one tailed,

independent) was used to compare continuous outcomes between the before and after periods. It was determined that P = 0.05 was significant. For the analysis, SPSS (version 20) software was utilized. Trial lasted from January 2016 until June 2017.A 150 women were screened, 100 were randomly assigned, and 48 women finished the study during this time.(40)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study Design:

This study utilize a cross-sectional observational design to compare the sonographic features of PCOS between married and unmarried females. Cross-sectional studies are effective in assessing the prevalence and characteristics of a particular condition or disease at a specific point in time.

Sampling Technique:

The study employed a convenience sampling technique. Participants are recruited from gynecological clinics, hospitals, and community health centers. Eligible participants are categorized into married and unmarried based on self-reported. The inclusion criteria involve females diagnosed with PCOS, aged between 18 and 45 years, who are either married or unmarried, and have not reached menopause. The exclusion criteria may include individuals with other endocrine disorders or significant comorbidities that might confound the results.

Sample Size:

The sample size is calculated by using this formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} P (1-P)}{nd^2}$$

Confidence level [%] 1- α =95%

Prevalence of PCOS P=5% to 15

Absolute precision required d=10%

Sample Size n=73

Data Collection:

Expert's doctors conduct Transvaginal ultrasound and scans by using standardized protocols. Parameters such as ovarian volume, follicle count, cyst size and other relevant features are recorded. Additional data such as duration of PCOS diagnosis and hormonal profiles also collected.

- **Sonographic Evaluation:** Transvaginal or transabdominal ultrasound is performed to assess the ovarian morphology and follicle count. Other sonographic parameters associated with PCOS, such as ovarian volume, stromal echogenicity, and presence of follicular cysts, is evaluated.

- **Demographic and Clinical Data:** Participants' demographic information (age, marital status) and relevant clinical data (menstrual history, hormonal profiles) is collected through structured interviews and medical record reviews.

- **Data Analysis:** Descriptive statistics is used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population. The sonographic findings of PCOS are compared between married and unmarried females using appropriate statistical tests, such as t-tests or chi-square tests. Regression analysis or other multivariable statistical models may be employed to control for potential confounders.

Study settings:

Data is collected from Arif memorial teaching hospital / Hameed Latif hospital / and other Government hospitals, Lahore

Data collection procedure:

In the duration of July 2023-january 2024, all patients having PCOS in their respective ages are referred to the gynecology department of Arif Memorial Teaching hospital .After taking consent from the patients , they enrolled in the study .Any abnormal findings are noticed. A complete physical examination of the uterus internal structure is done with the help of ultrasonography.

Pelvic ultrasound:

An ultrasound test using a transducer of frequency a 5MHZ of Toshiba Company is used to see the ovaries. In the transvaginal ultrasonography, a probe is inserted into the vagina.And transabdominal ultrasonography in which probe is placed on the abdomen. When an electric current is provided, the piezoelectric crystals vibrate and change this electrical current into mechanical energy and absorbed in the tissue. Only a few sound waves reflected back into the transducer and again vibrate the crystals, which then

change mechanical energy into electrical energy, and on the monitor is obtained.

Study duration:

The duration of study is 8 month.

Exclusion criteria:

Women reporting malignancy, diabetic and hypertension, renal failure and hepatic diseases are excluded from study group.

Inclusion criteria:

- Female patient come with sign and symptoms of PCOS.
- Female patients with PCOS either married and unmarried before menopause

Ethical Considerations:

The study is adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring informed consent, privacy, and confidentiality of participant data. Institutional review board (IRB) approval is sought before the commencement of the study.

Limitations:

- Selection bias: The convenience sampling method may introduce selection bias, limiting the generalizability of the results.
- Recall bias: Reliance on self-reported information may be prone to recall bias.
- Cross-sectional design: Being a cross-sectional study, it cannot establish a cause-and-effect relationship between marital status and the sonographic findings of PCOS

RESULTS

A total of 73 patient with PCOS are included in my research. Most of the patients (11%) with PCOS are from age group of 15to22 years, (6%) patients from age group of 23to30 years, (3%) patients from age group of 31 to 37 years, (2%) patients from age group of 38to45,45 patients (61%) belongs to middle class,37 patients (50%) are students,29 patients (39%) have habit of eating fast food,54 patients (74%) are unmarried,52 patients(71%) have reproductive health issues,48(61%) having irregular menses,59(80%) having hirsutism ,48(65%) having acne issues,44(60%) having weight issues14(20%) having poor quality of life.

Table 4.1. Age distribution among study sample.

Age	Missing	Mean	Standard Deviation
73	0.0	27.71	7.999

Interpretation:

In this table frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, results showed that mean age of study sample was 27.71 with standard deviation of 7.999.

- Mean =27.71
- Std.Dev=7.999
- N=73

Figure 4.1. Bar chart predicting age distribution among study sample.

Table 4.2. Frequency of education among study sample

Education	Frequency	Percent
Graduation	22	30.1%
M.Phil.	11	15.1%
Matric	24	32.9%

Uneducated	16	21.9%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this table frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, results showed that 1 (30%)

had PCOS in women with graduation, 1(13%) had PCOS in M.Phil. 1(32%) had PCOS in women with matric and 1(20%) had PCOS in women with uneducated.

Figure 4.2 predicting the frequency of education among study sample.

Table 4.3. Frequency of socioeconomic status among study sample.

Socioeconomic status	Frequency	Percent
Low	25	34.2%
Middle	45	61.6%
High	3	4.1%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 25(34.2%) had PCOS in

women with low socioeconomic status, 45(61.1%) had PCOS in women with middle status, and 3(4.1%) had PCOS in women with high socioeconomic status.

Figure 4.3 pie chart predicting frequency of socioeconomic status among study sample.

Table 4.4. Frequency of occupation among study sample.

Occupation	Frequency	Percent
students	37	50.7%
business	7	9.6%
teachers	5	6.8%
housewife	24	32.9%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 37(50%) students had

PCOS, 7 (9.6%) business women had PCOS, 5(6.8%) teachers had PCOS, 24(32.9%) housewives had PCOS.

• Figure 4.4. Pie chart predicting frequency of occupation among study sample.

• Table 4.5. Frequency of marital status among study sample.

Frequency of marital status	Frequency	Percent Marital status
Yes	19	26.0%
No	54	74.0%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size

n=73(100%) females, 19(26.0%) were married, 54(74.0%) were unmarried.

Figure 4.5. Bar chart predicting frequency of PCOS in married and unmarried females.

Table 4.6:

Previoup_PCOS_treatment

Previous PCOS treatment	Frequency	Percent
Yes	41	56.2%
No	32	43.8%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%)

41(56.2%) females had taken treatment of PCOS and 32(43.8) females has taken treatment.

Figure 4.6. Bar chart predicting relationship of PCOS with treatment of PCOS in women.

Table: 4.7 Reproductive health issues:

Reproductive health issues	Frequency	Percent
Yes	52	71.2%
No	21	28.8%

Total	73	100.0%
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- Interpretation:** In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 52(71.2%) women ha reproductive health issues and 21(28.8%) women had no reproductive health issues.

Figure 4.7. Bar chart predicting relationship of PCOS with reproductive health issues.

Table 4.8: Irregular menses:

Irregular menses	Frequency	Percent
Yes	48	65.8%
No	25	34.2%
Total	73	100.0%

- Interpretation:** In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 48(65.8%) females had irregular menses and 25(34.2%) females had no irregular menses.

Figure 4.8. Bar chart predicting relationship of PCOS with irregular menses.

Table 4.9: Hirsutism:

Hirsutism	Frequency	Percent
yes	59	80.8%

no	14	19.2%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

- In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size

n=73(100%) females, 59(80.0%) females had hirsutism and 14(19.2%) had no hirsutism.

Figure 4.9. Bar chart predicting relationship of PCOS with hirsutism in married and unmarried females.

Table 5.1. Acne:

Acne	Frequency	Percent
Yes	48	65.8%
no	25	34.2%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size

n=73(100%) females, 48(65.8%) females had acne and 25(34.2) females had no acne.

Figure 5.1. Bar chart predicting relationship of PCOS with acne.

• Table 5.2. Weight issues:

Weight issues	Frequency	Percent
Yes	44	60.3%
No	29	39.7%

Total	73	100.0%
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- Interpretation:**
 In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 44(60.3%) had weight issues and 29(39.7%) had no weight issues.

Figure 5.2. Bar chart depicting frequency of weight issues in women with PCOS

Table5.3: Years of marriage:

Years of marriage	Frequency	Percent
1	3	4.1%
2	5	6.8%
3	6	8.2%
4	1	1.4%
5	4	5.5%
6	19	26.0%
7	54	74.0%
Total	73	100.0%

- Interpretation:**
 In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 3(4.1%) had 1 year of marriage, 5(6.8%) had 2 years of marriage, 6(8.2%) had 3 years, 1(1.4%) had 4 years, 4(5.5%) had 5 years, 19(26.0%) had 6 years and 54(74.0%) had 7 years of marriage.

Figure 5.3. Pie chart predicting the frequency and relationship of PCOS in marital status.

Table 5.4: Quality of married life:

Quality of married life	Frequency	Percent
Poor	15	20.5%
Good	4	5.5%
Total	19	26.0%
System	54	74.0%
	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size

n=73(100%) female, 15(20.5%) had poor quality of life, 4(5.5%) had good quality of married life.

Figure 5.4. Pie chart predicting relationship of PCOS with quality o married life. 75% females had poor quality of married life and 35% had good quality of married life.

Table 5.5: Physical activity:

Physical activity	Frequency	Percent
yes	50	68.5
no	23	31.5
Total	73	100.0

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size

n=73(100%) females, 50(68.5%) had performed physical activity and 23(31.5%) had not performed physical activity.

Figure 5.5. Bar chart predicting the frequency of physical activity in PCOS patients.50% females had physical activity but 20% females had no physical activity.

Table 5.6 Dietary habits:

Dietary habits	Frequency	Percent
Balanced	19	26.0%
high sugar	25	34.2%
fast food	29	39.7%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 19(26.0%) females had

balanced diet, 25(34.2%) had high sugar diet and 29(39.7%) had fast food.

Figure 5.6.Pie chart predicting frequency of PCOS in females of different dietary habits. 30% females had dietary habit of balanced diet, 30% had dietary habits of high sugar and 40% females had dietary habits of fast food.

Table 5.7 Stress level:

Stress level

Stress level	Frequency	Percent
Low	50	68.5%
High	23	31.5%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%)

females, 50(68.5%) had low stress level and 23(31.5%) had high stress level.

Figure 5.7. Pie chart predicting the frequency of stress level in PCOS patients. 75% females had low level of stress and 35% females had high level of stress.

Table 5.8: Anxiety level:

Anxiety level	Frequency	Percent
rarely	20	27.4%
occasionally	32	43.8%
often	21	28.8%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this table frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%) females, 20(27.4%) had anxiety

rarely, 32(43.8%) had anxiety occasionally and 21(28.8%) had anxiety often.

Figure 5.8. Pie chart predicting relationship of PCOS with anxiety level. 40% females had stress occasionally, 30% had stress rarely and 30% had stress often ally.

Table 5.9: Genetics of PCOS:

Genetics of PCOS	Frequency	Percent
Yes	18	24.7%
No	55	75.3%
Total	73	100.0%

Interpretation:

In this chart frequency of PCOS among study sample. Study was conducted with sample size n=73(100%)

females, 18(24.7%) had genetics of PCOS and 55(75.3%) had no genetics of PCOS.

Figure 5.9. Bar chart predicting frequency of genetics of PCOS in study sample, 55% females had genetics of PCOS and 15% females had genetics of PCOS.

Discussion

PCOS is an endocrine disorder and its long-term complications. Nonetheless, it has been noted that altering one's lifestyle, using hormonal contraceptives, and using some medications such as inositol, clomiphene, eflornithine, finasteride, flutamide, letrozole, metformin, and spironolactone can lessen the symptoms of PCOS. This study is the longest follow-up investigation of anthropometric alterations, hirsutism presence, and reproductive hormone changes in PCOS-affected women.¹

During the 32 years of follow-up, but not during the final 11 years, FSH levels rose in the PCOS group. On the other hand, compared to controls, FSH levels were consistently lower in women with PCOS from perimenopause until senescence. During the 32 years of follow-up, but not during the final 11 years, FSH levels rose in the PCOS group. On the other hand, compared to controls, FSH levels were consistently lower in women with PCOS from perimenopause till senescence.²

The combination of hirsutism and weight increase has been shown to have a significant detrimental impact on quality of life in studies involving infertile women

with PCOS. Our findings suggest that the effects of hirsutism and overweight or obesity on quality of life continue beyond the reproductive age. Being overweight increases the likelihood of developing a number of diseases and exacerbates hyperandrogenism, which may account for the detrimental effects on one's quality of life.³ Compared to women without hyperactive androgenic symptoms, those with PCOS who exhibit

Hyperactive androgenic symptoms at the time of PCOS diagnosis are more likely to experience chronic androgenic symptoms as well as a lower quality of life in midlife. Few people received treatment for their symptoms at the same time. Physicians should try their hardest to relieve PCOS-afflicted women's symptoms not just during the reproductive years but also in later life. Women with PCOS should also be informed about their treatment options and health hazards.⁴

PCOS is still difficult to diagnose and treat, even though it affects many women of reproductive age. Insulin resistance is a nearly uniform finding in PCOS and is exacerbated by obesity associated with hyperandrogenism. Many obstacles still need to be

overcome in the management of PCOS. An important factor in morbidity is a high incidence of obesity. Given that early signs of PCOS are well-characterized, early attention to weight increase in infancy and adolescence in individuals at risk for PCOS may be a crucial preventive intervention.⁵

5 to 20% of women who are of reproductive age have PCOS, a common and complex endocrine condition. Clinical manifestations of PCOS encompass hirsutism, infertility, menstrual disruption, obesity, and metabolic syndrome. Clinical symptoms and metabolic consequences are quite variable. Although the exact cause of PCOS is unknown, four factors appear to have varying degrees of involvement in the syndrome: insulin resistance, partial folliculogenesis arrest, elevated ovarian and/or adrenal androgen production, and disruption of the neuroendocrine axis.⁶

Lean women with PCOS have different hormonal, metabolic, and hematological profiles from their healthy counterparts. Among contrast, the derangements were either similar or less pronounced among obese women who also had the syndrome. PCOS appeared to come with innate insulin resistance, regardless of fat. Treatment options included maintaining a healthy weight, using insulin-sensitizers like metformin to restore ovulation, relieving symptoms like menstrual dysfunction, acne, and hirsutism, and using assisted reproductive technologies in cases where ovulation was not restored. All of these approaches showed encouraging outcomes.⁷

Study is conducted with sample size n=73(100%)females, results showed that 1(20%) had PCOS at the age of 15, 1(20%) had PCOS at the age of 16, 4(27%) had PCOS at the age of 20, 5(6%) had PCOS at the age of 21, 1(10%) had at age of 22, 1(9%) had at age of 23, 1(4%) at the age of 24, 1(20%) at the age of 25, 3(4%) had PCOS at the age of 26, 2(2%) at the age of 27, 6(8%) had PCOS at the age of 29 5(6%) had PCOS at the age of 30. 1 (30%) had PCOS in women with graduation, 1(13%) had PCOS in M.Phil. 1(32%) had PCOS in women with matric and 1(20%) had PCOS in women with uneducated.

37(50%) students had PCOS, 7(9.6%) business women had PCOS, 5(6.8%) teachers had PCOS, 24(32.9%) housewives had PCOS. 19(26.0%) were

married, 54(74.0%) were unmarried. 25(34.2%) had PCOS in women with low socioeconomic status, 45(61.1%) had PCOS in women with middle status, and 3(4.1%) had PCOS in women with high socioeconomic status. 52(71.2%) women ha reproductive health issues and 21(28.8%) women had no reproductive health issues.

50(68.5%) had low stress level and 23(31.5%) females had high stress level, 18(24.7%) had genetics of PCOS and 55(75.3%) had no genetics of PCOS. 19(26.0%) females had balanced diet, 25 (34.2%) had high sugar diet and 29(39.7%) had fast food.

Conclusion

On the basis of our study, it is concluded that Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) are more common in unmarried women then married. Of women of reproductive age, 4.8% to 18.6% have polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), the most prevalent endocrinopathy in women. 3.39% to 8.03% of teenagers between the ages of 10 and 19 have PCOS.

Because symptoms of PCOS resemble typical puberty indicators, such as irregular menstrual cycles and acne, it can be challenging to confirm a diagnosis in adolescents. The diagnostic standards for determining the diagnosis of PCOS in teenagers were highlighted in new evidence-based guidelines published in 2018. Additionally, these guidelines suggest identifying adolescents who fall into the risk group and who need to be closely watched since they do not yet meet the diagnostic criteria for PCOS. Early diagnosis is crucial for initiating lifestyle changes related to this illness.

In addition to maintaining PCOS symptoms, increased body weight, which affects 40–70% of adolescents with PCOS, dramatically raises the risk of chronic non-communicable diseases in the future. Health-related quality of life is negatively impacted by PCOS and its symptoms (HRQOL). Patients with PCOS are more likely to engage in binge eating. Since lifestyle modifications are the most successful form of therapy, it is especially critical to identify patients who are more likely to develop PCOS, diagnose them at an early stage, and provide them with the most appropriate course of treatment that meets their needs and enhances their quality of life.

Limitations of the study:

- Selection bias: The convenience sampling method may introduce selection bias, limiting the generalizability of the results.
- Recall bias: Reliance on self-reported information may be prone to recall bias.
- Cross-sectional design: Being a cross-sectional study, it cannot establish a cause-and-effect relationship between marital status and the sonographic findings of PCOS.

Recommendations:

- During my study I, encountered considerable difficulties in procuring data.
- Our hospitals and whole educational system should extend a supportive role for researches like mine.
- More and more people should look into this area of medicine so that awareness can be spread and preventive measures must be taken to lessen the spread of this disease in developing nations like ours.
- PCOS is a common issue in the young women in Pakistan. We need much more in depth research to aid clinical management of this disease.
- There are many more noninvasive methods with better results than ultrasonography; our clinics should employ such technique to further enhance infertility treatments related to PCOS.

Implications:

This study can be implied in the area of education, research as well in clinical applications where it can provide a great insight for students, researchers, medical officers and other individuals in the area of medicine and knowledge.

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